

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF *IRVINGIA GABONENSIS* SEED FLOUR

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ABSTRACT

The *Irvingia gabonensis* seed has been evaluated with respect to proximate, mineral composition and functional properties. The seed contained (g/100g): protein (12.78), fibre (5.87), fat (40.26) and carbohydrate (37.47). The predominant metal in the seed is sodium (840mg/100g). Water absorption, oil absorption and oil emulsion capacities are relatively high, while foaming capacity and least gelation concentration are low. The results showed that the seed may be useful in some food formulations.

KEYWORDS: *Irvingia gabonensis*, mineral, proximate composition, functional properties.

INTRODUCTION

In many rural tropical communities, local-seeds from wild or semi-dome, herb trees and climbers, are used in the diet, often the oil is extracted and the crushed seed is added to soups and stews. An example of one of such seeds is that of the *Irvingia gabonensis*, sometimes known as "Wild mango" (FAO, 1989).

Wild mango is a large tree up to 120ft. high or more, with grey trunk slight buttressed. This tree is found in an evergreen forest and mixed deciduous forest, sometimes seen in villages or towns. The pulp, kernel and fruit are said to be eaten by man and animal, although bitter and acrid, with the flavour of turpentine. The fruits are rich in oil and are important because of their use in making bread, chocolate, cheese butter, soap and feed cake. The wood is suitable for planking of ships decks, wood paving, house post, canoes, pestles, for household utensils and the bark is medicinal (Irvine, 1961).

Some authors have reported the proximate compositions, metal contents and production of wine from this seed (Uzegbu, 1993; Ojukwu *et al*, 2000) elsewhere.

However, there is little or no information on the functional properties of the *Irvingia gabonensis* seed. Therefore, this present study investigated the chemical composition and the functional properties of the seed in an attempt to assess its value for application in the food industries.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The sample was obtained from a farm site in Arimogija, Ose Local Government area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The seed was carefully washed with distilled water, sun dried for 3 days, ground with a Kenwood blender and kept in a dry container prior to analyses. Proximate analysis of the sample for moisture, dry matter and crude fat were determined in triplicate using the methods described by AOAC (1990). Nitrogen was determined by the micro-Kjeldahl method described by Pearson (1976), and the result was used for estimating the crude protein content by multiplying by 6.25. The ash content was determined using the method described by Pearson (1976). Carbohydrate was determined by difference (100 – ash + protein + fibre + fat). Minerals were determined using a solution that was obtained by dry-ashing the sample at 550°C and dissolving it in distilled water that contains a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid in a volumetric flask. Na and K contents were measured with a Corning 405 flame photometer (AOAC, 1990). Fe, Mg and Ca were determined with a Perkin Elmer 306 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The

Table 1: Proximate and mineral constituents of samples analyzed (n=3)

Parameter	Mean±SD
Moisture (g/100g)	8.25 (0.76)
Ash	3.62 (0.22)
Protein	12.78 (0.79)
Fibre	5.87 (0.22)
Fat	40.26 (0.88)
Carbohydrate ^a	37.47 (0.72)
Calcium (mg/100g)	560 (3.42)
Potassium	110 (1.22)
Sodium	840 (5.22)
Magnesium	270 (1.98)
Iron	10 (0.15)
Phosphorus	240 (1.97)

n – number of determinations, a – calculated by difference

protein solubility of the sample was determined at various pH values by the method described by Oshodi and Ekperigin (1989). The least gelation concentration, water and oil absorption, and foaming properties of the sample were determined by the methods described by Sathe *et al* (1982).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 contains the proximate composition of the seed. The moisture content is low (8.25g/100g). This low value could be an added advantage to the shelf life of the seed. The ash content is low. This was depicted by standard deviation of 0.22. Fibre content (5.87g/100g) is low. Its ingestion will help to reduce blood cholesterol levels and the risk of bowel cancer and gall stones (Taylor *et al*, 1997). The fat content is high (40.26g/100g). This suggests that sample is a good source of vegetable oil. The carbohydrate content is 37.47g/100g. Carbohydrate makes up more than 82% of starch content. This means that the seed could be a good source of starch of human consumption and/or the industry. The above observation is in line with what was contained in other literature reports on soup thickeners (Uzuegbu, 1993), baobab seeds (Odetokun, 1996) and cooked seeds of locust beans (Adeyeye *et al*. 2002)

Table 1 also depicted the mineral contents of the sample in mg/100g. Sodium with a value of 840mg/100g was found to be the most abundant mineral in the seed. This observation is close agreement with what was reported by Uzuegbu (1993) and Odetokun, (1996). The results calcium, magnesium, phosphorus and potassium contents in our present study are different from the values reported for African yam bean (AYB) (Oshodi *et al.*, (1997); Adeparusi, (2001); Abdullahi; (2002). Iron concentration is the lowest mineral (10mg/100g) in the samples, hence seed may not be a good blood enhancing substance for the treatment of anemic patient.

Table 2 shows the results for the functional properties of the sample analysed. The water absorption capacity (WAC) of the seed is 150%. This value compared favourably with WAC reported for some seeds of AYB (Adeyeye and Aye, 1996; Oshodi *et al.*, 1997). *Cola acuminata* (Abulude, 2002) and breadnut (Nwabueze *et al.*, 2001). WAC has been very useful in the production of viscous foods. Hence, *Irvingia gabonensis* seed may be useful in the production of soups, gravies and doughs. Oil absorption capacity (OAC) is found to be 217%. This value is high than the values and for *Adenopus breviflorus* benth flour (Oshodi, 1992) and AYB (Oshodi *et al.*, 1997). The result is however, similar to those reported by Fagbemi and Olaofe (2000) for precooked cocoyam flour. In food formulation OAC plays a vital role in increasing the mouth feel of foods and acts as flavour retainer (Kinsella, 1976a). Least gelation concentration (LGC) is 10%. This result compared well with values reported in the literature. The LGC

low value might have been caused by the high value of the carbohydrate content in the seed. Subsequently, the seed may be useful in the production of curd or as an additive to other materials for forming gel in food

Table 2: Functional properties of sample analyzed (%)

Parameter	Mean±SD
Water Absorption Capacity	150 (1.40)
Oil Absorption Capacity	217 (1.98)
Least Gelation Concentration	10 (0.42)
Foaming Capacity	35 (0.72)
Oil Emulsion Capacity	97 (0.53)

Table 3: Protein Solubility (%) as a function of pH

pH	Protein Solubility
2	82
3	76
4	71
5	45
6	48
7	52
8	65
9	50
10	70
11	76
12	81

product. The values recorded for foaming capacity (FC) in this study is higher than those reported in literature. The high FC will enhance the seeds functionality in the production of cakes and whipping toppings (Kinsella, 1976b). The oil emulsion capacity (OEC) is 97%. This value is higher than that reported for locust beans (Adeyeye *et al.*, 2002). Hence, this seed may be ideal as an additive for the stabilization of emulsion in sausages (Altschul and Wilcke, 1985). Table 3 shows the results of the effect of pH on the solubility of the *Irvingia gabonensis* seed. It shows that a minimum solubility occurs in pH 5 and 9, and this corresponds to the iso-electric point of proteins and amino acids are least soluble at their iso electric points.

CONCLUSION

The present results show that the seed has high carbohydrate, fat and mineral contents. The functional properties were good and so this seed may have great potentials for food formulations.

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